

NETRA KRIYA KALPA – TARPAN AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN DAILY LIFE

*¹Dr. Chetan Narayan Gotad, ²Dr. Tushar firke

¹Final year. Shalaky Tantra SMBT Ayurvedic College, Dhamangaon, Igatpuri Nashik.

²Professor and HOD Dept. of Shalaky Tantra, SMBT Ayurvedic College Dhamangaon
Igatpuri Nashik.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Chetan Narayan Gotad

Final year. Shalaky Tantra SMBT
Ayurvedic College, Dhamangaon,
Igatpuri Nashik.

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ABSTRACT

Sarvendriyanam Nayanam pradhanam. That is eyes are the most important organ in human body and so care should be taken to protect them. Shalaky Tantra is a branch of Ashtanga Ayurveda which deals with study of diseases which occurs above Urdhva jatrugat bhaga of shareer. In this modern era and continuous use of electronic gadgets and use of mobiles increase screen time we need to protect the precious organ Eyes. Tarpan kriya kalpa its holistic approach towards positive life style Creates its inevitable significance in the present scenario. Tarpan Kriya Kalpa is main therapeutic process for Netraroga which is described in Sushruta Samhita Uttaratantra chapter 18, Vagbhata in Sutrasthana, Charaka in Chikitsa Sthana, Sharangdhar Samhita Uttara 13, Chakradatta chapter 76. Tarpan kriya kalpas are the main therapeutic procedures that are explained for both Management and prevention of eye diseases. In this article an effort has been made to Analyse the

mode of action of Tarpan kriya kalpas.

KEYWORDS: kriya kalpa, Tarpan, shalaky Tantra, Urdhva jatrugat bhaga.

INTRODUCTION

In Samhita granth, the local Treatment procedures for Netra Rogas are explained In the name of Netra Kriyakalpa. The word Kriya Means therapeutic action and Kalpa means specific Formulations. Tarpan is Chikitsa which is Brimhana (nourishing) in nature. It is also

commonly known as Netra Basti or Akshita arpana.^[1] Netra refers to eyes and Basti stands for means to hold (compartment which holds) or retaining something inside, in this case mainly medicated ghee. Tarpana is a procedure in which comfortably warm medicated ghee is kept over the eyes for a certain period of time with the help of a specially formed frame ring prepared from black gram powder.

Tarpana is a Snigdha Kriya Indicated in Vata Dusta ophthalmic conditions mainly in Dristigata Rogas. Ayurvedic therapeutics (Kriyakalpa) helps in maintaining Swasthya and to cure diseases.

Kriya= Therapeutic action Kalpa= specific formulation of medicines.

Netra Tarpan It is one of the prime and widely practiced kriya kalpa; it aims to give Nourishment to the eyes and cures the vata Pitta vikara (preventive as well as curative Aspects).

Tarpan karma

1) Purva Karma (Pre-treatment procedure)

1. Preparation of patient
2. Examination of patient
3. Explanation of procedure.

2). Preparation for the treatment

Materials: Ghruta (medicated ghee), Flour of black Gram for the construction of Netra Tarpana socket, Induction, bowls. Vessels, spoons Sterile cloth/cotton. Sterile preparation of the items- required items like cloth, Cotton, bowl, and spoon are sterile with autoclave Sterilization method.

Sharir shodhan

Vamana Therapeutic emesis (vomiting) and **Virechana**-Therapeutic purgation **Shiro-Shuddhi**. Head cleansing measure (treatments Meant for purifying and detoxifying head and sense Organs) i.e. **Nasya** or Shiro-virechana (Nasal Instillation of medications)

3) Preparing the flour pali, Flour of black gram will be Mixed thoroughly in a sterile vessel by adding water and Little. The mixture is made into a bolus. From this, 2 Small rings so as to fit around the eye socket are Prepared. That means to tell that the inner circumference of the ring will fit on the boundary of the socket of the Eye so as to enclose the eye within it. The height of the Ring should be of 2 angula^[2]

4) Tarpan sneha drava ghee which would be used For Netra Tarpanam shall be liquefied and kept lukewarm For this, the required quantity of ghee is put in a small Sterile bowl.

Fomentation sthanik swedan – A gentle fomentation is given to the Eyes with cloth dipped in warm water before the Treatment.

5) The Medicated ghee (ghrita) which was melted and kept Warm in the Purvakarma is gently poured in the Netra Tarpan pali (Rings) such that the eyes are dipped within the Medicine. The patient is advised to close the eyes while Dropping the medicine in the ring. Later he or she is Instructed to open and close the eyes repeatedly so that The interior of eyes come into the contact of the Medicines intermittently. The medicaments are left in Place for a fixed duration of time. The patient might Experience burning sensation during the process of the Treatment but he or she should be intimated that it is quiet Natural to happen. The irritation will come down once, The medicines (ghrut) is removed.

Pachat karma

The medicine is removed By creating a small. Hole in the lower portion of the Wall of the flour ring at the outer angle of the eye And draining the contents in a bowl. Alternately, the Wall of the ring is broken at the outer canthus (outer Angle of the eye) and the contents are drained in a Bowl. Wiping the eyes and the surrounding area The Medicines sticking to the eye and the sockets are Swabbed out by wiping them off with the help of a Sterile cotton pad or a tissue paper. Later the eyes Can be wiped off gently with a sterile cloth dipped in Warm water or the same cloth is used to give a Gentle fomentation to the eyes.

Dhumapana- Herbal Smoking should be given to Eliminate the Kapha which has been exaggerate.

Doses of drug- Approx 35 ml for both eyes.

According to various acharya following are samyak, asamyak Tarpan laksha.

Indications of Netra Tarpan^[3]

- 1) Tamyati -feeling of darkness in front of eyes (also Due to irritation after exposure to light).
- 2) Ati vishushkam -excessive dryness of the eyes.
- 3) Ati daruna- eyes appear to have hardened.
- 4) Sheena pakshma -eye lashes falling down.
- 5) avila netram- dirtiness of eyes.
- 6) Jihma netram -abnormal deviation of eye ball.
- 7) Roga klishtam -eyes which have been constantly and Repeatedly afflicted and debilitated due to many Diseases.

Contra-indications of Netra Tarpan

- 1) Durdina – cloudy day
- 2) Atyushna dina -very hot day
- 3) Ati sheeta dina – very cold day
- 4) Chinta-person who is mentally worried
- 5) Aayasa- after physical exhaustion
- 6) Bhrama- giddiness
- 7) Ashanta upadrava -when complications like Inflammation, redness, severe pain etc persists in the Eye.

Indications and correlation

Visual disturbances – timira, avila darsana

Dry eye conditions – rooksha, parisushka, Ativisushka

Allergic conditions – klishtha vartma

Diseases of eye lids – hardened painful

Eyelids and damaged eyelashes

Structural deformities – squint, Shrunken

Eyeball: Difficulty in the movement of eyeball and

Eyelids: Stabdhata, krichronmeelana

Diseases of Sukla mandala – Sirotkata, Siraharsha, Arjuna

Diseases of Krishna mandala – Savrana Sukla, Avranasukla,

Diseases of Sarvagatha – Abhisyaanda, Sushkakaksi paaka, Anyatovata, Vataparyaya

Diseases of Drushtimandala – Timira, Kacha, Linganasha, Hruswajadya, etc

Tarpan matra according to the dosa

Doshabheda	Sushrut samhita	Astang Hriday	Shanrangadhar		Bhavprakash
Healthy eye	500 matra		500 matra	500 matra	500 matra
Kapha prakopa	600 matra		500 matra	500 matra	500matra
Pitta prakopa	800 matra		600 matra	-	600 matra
Vata prakopa	1000 matra		1000 matra	1000matra	1000 matra

Tarpan matra adhishtan

Adhishtan	Sushrut samhita	Ashtang Hriday	Sharangadhar samhita	Bhavprakash
Sandhigata	300	300	500	500
Vartmagata	100	100	100	100
Shuklagata	500	500	600	
Krishnagata	700	700	700	700
Drishtigata	800/1000	800	800	800
Sarvagata	1000	1000	1000	1000

PROBABLE MODE OF ACTION

In Tarpana sneha dravyas are Used, so it will cross corneal epithelium Easily as it is having lipophilic and Hydrophilic property Even contact time is More, so drug absorption is more. These Procedures enhance lubrication and do Nourishment of all structures of the eyes. First of all Sthanika mrudu snehana & swedana was given (this could have helped in dilation of conjunctival sac & limbal vessels which in turn helps in better absorption) Topically instilled medications largely penetrate intraocularly through the cornea.

Importance of Tarpan in Daily life

In this modern era the use of electronic gadgets like Mobile, television, excessive exposure to screen light can led to dryness, asthenopic strain on eye which can less to Refractive error at Early age, astigmatism, and other ocular pathologies, also deficiency disorder like vit A, vit C can leds to xerophthalmia, Use of Various Ghrit kalpana, Triphala, Mahatriphla ghrit^[4] can reduce the dryness, strain provide localized strength by fullfilling Nutritional Deficiencies.

urban lifestyle, poor hygiene, over use of screen exposure are new disease which ,an ophthalmologist face in his daily practice, Tarpan kriya kalpa is found to be most efficiently effective.

Tarpan Netra kriya kalpas has several advantages Over oral administration.

The drugs given orally will undergo Digestion under the influence of pachaka Pitta. The drugs administered through kriya Kalpa are not digested by it and possibly Rectify accumulated dosha.

1. The oral drugs find it difficult to cross the 3 major anatomical barriers in the eye such As blood-aqueous, blood-vitreous and blood-Retinal barriers to reach the target tissues of The eye. The topical drugs can cross and Reach the target tissue and achieve higher Bio-availability and desired action.
2. The corneal layers have a special Absorption mechanism – pharmaco-Kinetically. Corneal epithelium is lipophilic; Stroma- hydrophilic, endothelium behaves Lipophilic, Hence for issues of drug, Absorption across cornea one must consider The tri-laminar i.e. lipid – water –lipid, Domain of various anatomical layers.
3. The tissue contact time of the drugs can Be controlled in Tarpan kriya kalpa and they are Selected depending upon the stage and Severity of the disease.
4. The medications can be judiciously Selected. i.e, to increase ushna or sheeta, Snigdha or rooksha in the local area. Thus High concentration of the drug can be Achieved by applying the medicines.
5. The action of Tarpan kriya kalpas is faster Whereas the action of internal medicine is Time consuming and late. Thus high concentration of the drug can be Achieved by applying the medicines to eye. Procedures is mainly used for external Segmental disorders of eye (vartma gata Sandhi, shukla, Krishna mandala diseases) And as a purva upakrama of tarpana for Internal segmental disorders of eye (sarvagata and drustimandala).

CONCLUSION

Tarpan Netra Kriya-kalpas is well designed procedures To treat ocular disorders outlined by our Acharyas. They were aware of the Mechanism of blood- aqueous, blood-Vitreous, blood-retinal barriers. Thus topical Application of drugs is more beneficial than Oral route especially in ophthalmic Disorders. Kriyakalpas are the boon to Ayurveda. Netra Tarpan has Its own mode of action which helps in treating eye Disease. The aim of Kriyakalpa

procedures are seems To be tissue oriented where the therapeutic Concentration of the drug can be achieved by Concentration of drug, tissue contact time, molecular Weight of drug, absorption of drug, bio-availability of Drug.

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